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Spatial analysis and efficiency of healthcare delivery system in Meghalaya State, India: A 'Z' Score Approach

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Abstract

The study investigates the spatial distribution, significance, and efficiency of the healthcare delivery system in the northeastern state of Meghalaya, India. Utilising secondary data from the Statistical Handbook of 2022 and analytical techniques including Z-score standardisation and correlation matrix analysis via SPSS, the study highlights disparities in healthcare access and performance across districts. Findings reveal that districts like East Khasi Hills and West Garo Hills, which are better connected and urbanized, demonstrate higher healthcare efficiency, while remote and underdeveloped districts face infrastructural and personnel deficits. The research emphasises the need for decentralization, equitable distribution of healthcare infrastructure, community-level engagement, and integration of modern medical technologies. The study proposes strategic recommendations to strengthen primary health care (PHC) and improve health outcomes, particularly for underserved populations. When it comes to health care efficiency based on Z Score ranking, East Khasi Hills, West Jaintia Hills and West Garo Hills have the highest score in terms of being the most efficient district in health care delivery in Meghalaya state.

Keywords: Healthcare Delivery System; Spatial Distribution; Z-Score Analysis; Primary Health Care (PHC); GIS

1. Introduction

The primary health centre is essential health care made universally accessible to individuals and families in the community using providing essential drugs and medicines [1,2,3]. The community services offered by the PHC are prevention delivery system the and control of endemic diseases and environmental health programmes[4,5,6,7]. A health care organisation of people, institutions, and resources that deliver health care services to meet the health needs of target populations[8,9,10]. Effective primary health care relies on seamless coordination between various healthcare providers and services.

Health is influenced by several factors such as adequate food, housing, basic sanitation, healthy lifestyles, protection against environmental hazards and communicable diseases[11,12,13]. The frontiers of health extend beyond the narrow limits of medical care[14,15,16]. Thus, it is said that health care is more than medical care[17,18,19]. Health care embraces a multitude of services provided to individuals or communities by agents of health services or professions, to promote, maintain, monitor or restore health[20,21,22,23].

Health is a common theme in all nations of the world. Health has evolved over the centuries from a concept of concern for an individual to a worldwide social goal and encompasses the whole quality of life [24,25,26]. Health is a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of diseases or infirmity [27,28, 29].

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The main reason for the lack of health consciousness of the people, especially in rural areas is the burden of poverty that has set a major hurdle for getting access to health care[30,31,32,33]. The majority of the population depends on the government-run facilities, which is not very well equipped with all the latest medical facilities, which are at par with the latest technology of medical sciences[34,35,36]. which leads to the un treatability of the more severe illnesses, and this leads to patients being referred to private health care facilities in the city, which leads to their spending, which has greatly led to financial problems for those families[37,38,39,40].

Meghalaya is a state that is situated in a hilly region, the accessibility to health care facilities is very difficult owing to its terrain and the remoteness of some areas. Additionally, the health care facilities are not evenly or equally distributed in all the districts of the state and are concentrated more in the state capital and some major towns, which are the district headquarters of those districts.

Objectives

- The main objectives of this dissertation are given as follows: -
- To analyze the spatial distribution of the health care delivery system in Meghalaya.
- To analyze the significance of the health care delivery system and its efficacy.
- To find out the efficient health care district in Meghalaya.

1.1. Study Area

Meghalaya, 'the Abode of Clouds' is one of the North Eastern states of India. It was carved out of Assam to become an autonomous district on April 2, 1970 and was declared a full fledged state of the Indian Union on January 21, 1972. It lies between latitudes 25°02' and 26°07' N and longitudes 89°49'and 92°50'E, with a geographical area of 22,429 sq. Km and an elevation range from 60m to 1961m as (Laitkor Peak at 1961m is the highest) (Fig1). The climate is of monsoon type with distinct warm-wet and cold dry periods. Cherrapunji and Mawsynram, located in the southern part are the rainiest spots of the world. Meghalaya is predominantly a tribal state and inhabited by mainly 3 tribal communities, namely Khasis, Jaintias and Garos who account for 89% of the total population. There are, however other tribes like the Kochs, the Hajong, the Rabhas, the Mikirs and others who are also the aboriginals of the state.

Figure 1 Study Area Map of Meghalaya

2. Data Source and Methodology

2.1. Sources of Data

The data collected for the present study are mainly based on the information provided by the government departments which is through the Statistical Hand Book of 2022 issued by the Directorate of Economics and Statistics Government of Meghalaya, the collected information who are availing these health care services and secondary which are gathered from various sources.

2.2. Secondary Data

The demographic and social variables for Meghalaya were obtained from statistical handbook on Meghalaya for the year 2022 from the Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Shillong. The other statistical data were collected from respective offices. The study area maps and related information were obtained from the statistical handbook for Meghalaya 2022.

2.3. Techniques Used

A Z-Score is a statistical measurement of a score's relationship to the mean in a group of scores. A Z-score of 0 means the score is the same as the mean. A Z-score can be positive or negative, indicating whether it is above or below the mean and by how many standard deviations. A 'Z' score is a statistical measurement of a score's relationship to the mean in a group of scores [41, 42, 43]. A 'Z' score can also be positive or negative indicating whether it is above or below the mean and standard deviation. Z' score can also be explained as in addition of showing a score's relationship to the mean. The 'Z' score shows statistical data set. One real life application of 'Z' score is an usability testing's score is arrived at by calculating the difference so derived is divided by the standard deviation of the population [44, 45,46].

$$z = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}$$

2.4. Tools and Techniques

The relationships and the interdependent nature of different variables are analysed using the correlation matrix, capable of explaining the relationships of one variable with all other variables. Correlation matrix which is derived by using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social science), Standardised score ('Z' Score) techniques are the methods of scale transformation used to analyze the factors of socio-economic and health[47,48,49].

3. Results

The spatial and statistical analysis of the health care delivery system in Meghalaya reveals significant disparities in the distribution and availability of health infrastructure and human resources across the eleven districts of the state. The results derived using Z score analysis (through SPSS 14.0) and mapped using QGIS demonstrate the following key findings: According to Z score analysis, the region may be classified into 4 categories, such as very high representing values of (more than 0.50), High (0- 0.50) moderate (-0.50- 0) and low (less than -0.50). All the maps in this chapter are created by using Z score values and classified spatially according to figures.

3.1. Distribution of Primary Health Centres (PHCs)

The spatial analysis of PHCs highlights that East Khasi Hills district stands out with the highest Z score (2.55), indicating a very high concentration of PHCs (Table 1). This can be attributed to the district's urbanisation, higher population density, and presence of the state capital, Shillong (Fig 2). In contrast, South West Khasi Hills shows a very low Z score (-1.06), reflecting the lowest number of PHCs due to its recent bifurcation from West Khasi Hills and underdeveloped health infrastructure (Fig 3). In contrast, districts with rugged terrain and sparse population like South West Khasi Hills face logistical challenges, resulting in fewer health centres and limited accessibility to healthcare services.

Figure 2 Spatial Distribution of PHCs Meghalaya

Figure 3 Number of Primary health centre

Table 1 Number of PHCs Meghalaya

District	PHCs	Z Score Value
East Khasi Hills	27	-0.72
West Khasi Hills	5	0.31
South West Khasi Hills	4	-0.38
Eastern West Khasi Hills	11	2.55
Ri Bhoi	9	0.83
West Jaintia Hills	11	-1.06
East Jaintia Hills	6	0.14
West Garo Hills	11	-0.55
South West Garo Hills	9	-0.20
East Garo Hills	8	-0.72
South Garo Hills	6	-0.20
North Garo Hills	9	0.83
TOTAL	116	

3.2. Availability of Doctors

A similar trend is seen in the distribution of doctors. East Khasi Hills again scores the highest (2.42), supported by the presence of specialised medical facilities and higher patient inflow from nearby districts (Table 2). West Garo Hills (1.33) follows due to its regional prominence. East Jaintia Hills (-0.84) has the least number of doctors, reflecting infrastructural challenges and limited health centres (Fig 4).

Table 2 Number of Doctors

Sl No.	Districts	Z Score
1	East Jaintia Hills	-0.84
2	West Jaintia Hills	0.02
3	Ri Bhoi	-0.13
4	East Khasi Hills	2.42
5	West Khasi Hills	-0.06
6	South West Khasi Hills	-0.74
7	North Garo Hills	-0.65
8	East Garo Hills	-0.28
9	West Garo Hills	1.33
10	South Garo Hills	-0.52
11	South West Garo Hills	-0.54

Sources: compiled by author

Figure 4 Number of Doctors

3.3. Availability of Pharmacists

The concentration of pharmacists correlates with the number of health centres. East Khasi Hills scores the highest (2.73), indicating an adequate number of pharmacists serving the population. South West Khasi Hills (-0.85) again records the lowest, reinforcing the district's underserved status (Table 3:Fig 5).

Table 3 Number of Pharmacists

Sl No.	Districts	Z Score
1	East Jaintia Hills	-0.58
2	West Jaintia Hills	0.23
3	Ri Bhoi	-0.37
4	East Khasi Hills	2.73
5	West Khasi Hills	0.44
6	South West Khasi Hills	-0.85
7	North Garo Hills	-0.37
8	East Garo Hills	-0.44
9	West Garo Hills	0.37
10	South Garo Hills	-0.58
11	South West Garo Hills	-0.58

Sources: compiled by author

Figure 5 Number of Pharmacists

3.4. Healthcare Efficiency

Efficiency, assessed through multiple indicators (infrastructure, manpower, and accessibility), shows that East Khasi Hills (Z score 119), West Garo Hills (94), and West Jaintia Hills (82) are the most efficient districts. These districts are urbanized hubs and administrative centres with better transportation and healthcare networks (Table 4). Conversely, South West Khasi Hills (24) and South Garo Hills (31) are the least efficient, largely due to rugged terrain, sparse population, and limited healthcare reach. (Fig 6). Factors contributing to this inefficiency include difficult terrain, lower population density, poor road connectivity, and underdeveloped healthcare infrastructure [50,51,52,53]. These districts suffer from delays in emergency medical response, poor immunization outreach, and limited availability of diagnostic services.

3.5. Availability of Medical Manpower

A similar pattern is observed in the distribution of doctors and pharmacists. East Khasi Hills ($Z=2.42$ for doctors, $Z=2.73$ for pharmacists) leads due to its extensive healthcare network and the presence of specialist services. The presence of tertiary care institutions and referral centres in Shillong attracts more medical professionals to the region. Conversely, districts like East Jaintia Hills (-0.84 for doctors) and South West Khasi Hills (-0.85 for pharmacists) have significantly fewer medical personnel, resulting in lower service availability and increased patient load in nearby urban centres. The imbalance in the distribution of medical professionals correlates directly with the availability of PHCs. Districts with fewer PHCs also have lower human resource deployment, reflecting a systemic gap in healthcare planning and service delivery [54,55,56].

3.6. Immunization and Family Welfare Services

Immunization coverage is highest in East Khasi Hills and West Khasi Hills, indicating better outreach and public health awareness. Family welfare services also show uneven distribution, with urban districts having better facilities and awareness campaigns.

Table 4 Z score value of Health Care Delivery System in Meghalaya

District	Primary Health Centre	Community Health Centre	Sub Centre	Doctors	Nurses	Pharmacist	Lab Technicians	Vaccinator	ANM	Health Visitors	General Beds	Fully Immunized	BCG completed doses	TT for pregnant women	Measles vaccine	Family Welfare Clinics	Rural	Urban	No. of patients treated	Total
West Jaintia Hills	0.31	0.28	0.31	0.02	-0.16	0.23	0.33	0.18	0.26	1.56	-0.04	0.56	0.34	0.26	0.57	0.29	0.31	0.02	0.41	0.41
Ri Bhoi	-0.38	0.28	-0.42	-0.13	-0.27	-0.37	0.04	-0.76	-0.59	-0.69	-0.19	-0.30	-0.34	-0.11	-0.27	-0.38	-0.38	-0.49	0.73	0.63
East Khasi Hills	2.55	2.31	1.88	2.42	2.90	2.73	2.59	2.64	2.58	2.26	2.77	2.14	2.57	2.32	2.09	2.33	2.22	2.84	2.63	2.63
West Khasi Hills	0.83	-0.23	0.31	-0.06	-0.12	0.44	0.42	0.18	-0.06	-0.35	0.33	0.99	0.29	0.54	1.03	0.32	0.35	0.02	0.08	0.14
South West Khasi Hill	-1.06	-0.23	-1.32	-0.74	-0.62	-0.85	-0.99	-0.76	-1.26	-0.69	-0.83	-0.82	-0.73	-0.88	-0.84	-1.12	-1.19	-0.49	-0.64	-0.67
North Garo Hills	0.14	-0.74	0.49	-0.65	-0.54	-0.37	-0.52	-0.52	0.12	-0.17	-0.68	-0.72	-0.52	-0.55	-0.75	0.18	0.31	-0.49	-0.77	-0.76
East Garo Hills	-0.55	-0.74	-0.60	-0.28	-0.27	-0.44	-0.43	-0.52	-0.34	-0.87	-0.45	-0.74	-0.55	-0.62	-0.74	-0.56	-0.58	-0.49	-0.49	-0.52
West Garo Hills	-0.20	1.29	1.46	1.33	0.36	0.37	0.51	0.53	0.68	-0.17	0.45	0.92	0.86	1.14	0.95	1.03	1.08	0.53	-0.08	0.03
South Garo Hills	-0.72	-0.74	-0.90	-0.52	-0.38	-0.58	-0.81	-0.05	-0.68	-0.52	-0.49	-0.91	-0.72	-0.84	-0.91	-0.95	-1.02	-0.49	-0.65	-0.67

Figure 6 Healthcare Efficiency

3.7. Overall Spatial Pattern

The spatial patterns indicate that districts with better connectivity, higher urbanization, and administrative significance tend to perform better in terms of healthcare delivery. Districts with difficult terrain and rural settlements lag behind in infrastructure and healthcare accessibility.

4. Discussion

The health care delivery system in Meghalaya presents a complex picture of progress and challenges. The spatial analysis using Z scores has revealed substantial disparities in the distribution and accessibility of primary healthcare infrastructure across the eleven districts of the state. The rugged terrain and dispersed rural population play a significant role in shaping the healthcare landscape. Districts such as East Khasi Hills, West Garo Hills, and West Jaintia Hills consistently perform better in terms of the number of PHCs, availability of doctors, pharmacists, and overall healthcare efficiency. These districts benefit from higher population density, better road connectivity, urbanization, and proximity to administrative centers. East Khasi Hills, in particular, houses the state capital, Shillong, and leads in nearly all healthcare parameters due to its advanced infrastructure and concentration of medical manpower.

In contrast, South West Khasi Hills, South Garo Hills, and East Jaintia Hills reflect lower healthcare indicators. These districts are relatively new or geographically challenged, leading to limited health infrastructure and medical staff. Poor connectivity and lower population density further exacerbate the challenges of providing equitable healthcare services in these regions.

The study highlights that while PHCs are the backbone of rural healthcare, their uneven spatial distribution has led to inefficiencies in healthcare access. The same trend is observed in the availability of doctors and pharmacists, further widening the healthcare gap. Notably, districts with better healthcare infrastructure also report higher immunization coverage and family welfare service delivery, reinforcing the importance of robust local healthcare systems. The efficiency of healthcare delivery, as quantified by Z-score analysis, reveals a direct correlation between the level of urbanization, infrastructure development, and healthcare outcomes. High-performing districts serve as regional healthcare hubs, often catering to surrounding areas due to the lack of facilities elsewhere.

5. Conclusion

The study concludes that Meghalaya's healthcare delivery system, though functioning, is unevenly distributed and influenced by a combination of topographical, demographic, and infrastructural factors. Districts with better connectivity and urban development like East Khasi Hills and West Garo Hills demonstrate higher efficiency and better

access to healthcare services. Conversely, remote districts struggle with inadequate facilities, insufficient health personnel, and limited service delivery. The findings underscore the urgent need for a more balanced distribution of PHCs and healthcare staff, particularly in under-served districts. Investments in road infrastructure, health awareness, and capacity-building of healthcare workers, especially lab technicians and pharmacists, are essential for strengthening the system. To ensure equitable healthcare for all, policies must focus on decentralizing health services, empowering community-level health workers, and integrating modern medical technologies at the primary level. Only through such inclusive and strategic interventions can Meghalaya move towards a more efficient and accessible healthcare system, ultimately improving health outcomes and quality of life for its people. When it comes to health care efficiency based on Z Score ranking East Khasi Hills, West Jaintia Hills and West Garo Hills has the highest score in terms of being the most efficient district in health care delivery because it hoes the state capital which covers more of an urban area whereby at the same time have a high population and also have better developed health care infrastructure that can cater to needs of the people.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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